

Study of base line environmental data of fluorspar mining with special reference to Kadipani mine (Gujarat)

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Abstract : Any mining activity is likely to affect the quality of surrounding environment during its operation. The nature and magnitude of impacts on different components of the environment, viz. air, noise, water, land, biological and socio-economic vary depending on the nature and size of the mining project and therefore it is essential to find out the base line environmental data before preparing the environmental management plan. Environment management plan gives the account of measures necessary to prevent the impacts on the baseline environmental situations. Once the base line status of environmental parameters is known the decision regarding corrective and preventive measures becomes more scientific and technologically and financially viable. In present study efforts are made to establish the base line air and water quality of Kadipani District, Vadodara, Gujarat. Therefore this study is useful for making the decisions regarding the environmental measures required by the mining activity.

Keywords : Ground water, surface water, soil, air impacts, ambient air quality, environmental management plan.

Introduction

The study was carried out near the fluorspar mine at Ambadungar Kadipani, Distt., Vadodara, Gujarat. A 10 km radius area from the core mining site was first selected and then air quality was monitored using the high volume sampler. The sampling network was designed keeping in view the prevailing wind directions¹ and potential impact zones around the proposed project site. Based on this, eight ambient air quality-monitoring stations³ were selected and monitoring was carried out twice in a week at each sampling station for three months during the summer season in the year 2008 as summer is a critical season from environmental pollution dispersion point of view. At all these stations, Suspended Particulate Matter (SPM) was monitored on 24 hourly basis. Similarly the underground and surface water samples were analysed for knowing the physico-chemical parameters viz. physical, inorganic, organic and nutrients and heavy metals in laboratory.

Experimental

Air environment :

The SPM¹ was monitored by gravimetric method using High Volume Sampler. The Whatman glass fiber fil-

ter paper ¹GS/A was first maintained at 200 °C for 24 h and then weighed². The filter paper was then fitted to the High Volume Sampler and samples were collected at 1200 L/min for 24 h. Filter paper was again weighed and amount of particulate matter per unit volume are calculated. SO₂ and NO_x were found out using Pulse Fluorescent Instrument and Chemiluminescence Instrument respectively.

Water environment :

Physico-chemical analysis of water⁴ :

Turbidity :

Hach model 2100 P turbidometer was used to measure turbidity. Calibration is carried out with the standards of < 0.1 NTU, 20, 100 and 800 NTU stabilized formazin solutions².

pH and electrical conductivity (EC) :

The pH and EC were determined using Hach model pH meter and SENSION conductivity meter.

Total solids, suspended solids (TS), dissolved solids (TDS) were determined by gravimetric method by evaporating the sample to dryness at 103–105 °C for 24 h. The residue left after evaporation was weighed and calculations were made.

Organic and nutrient parameter :

Dissolved oxygen (D.O.) :

Dissolved oxygen was calculated using Winkler method.

Phosphate was determined by Hach model 2010 spectrophotometer using Phosver 3 Ascorbic acid method (range 0.00 to 2.50 mg/L).

COD : Standard reflux method was used.

Chemical analysis⁴ :

Alkalinity (HCO₃⁻) :

Alkalinity of sample was estimated by titrating with standard sulfuric acid.

Chlorides (Cl⁻) :

Chloride was determined by titration with standard silver nitrate, using potassium chromate as an indicator as described in soil analysis.

Sulphate (SO₄²⁻) :

Sulfate ions were precipitated as BaSO₄ in acidic media (HCl) with barium chloride. The absorption of light by this precipitated suspension was measured by spectrophotometer at 450 nm.

Hardness :

Hardness due to calcium and magnesium was determined by standard complexometric titration (EDTA titration method).

Fluorides (F⁻) :

Fluorides were estimated by spectrophotometric method using Hach model 2010 (Standard SPADNS method).

Nitrogen (ammonia) :

Nitrogen (ammonia) was determined spectrophotometrically (Hach model 2010) by Standard Nessler method. Program number 380 was entered in the instrument and corresponding wavelength of 425 nm (range 0 to 2.50 mg/L) was dialed. 1 ml nessler reagent was added in the 25 ml of sample and 25 ml of de-ionised water (blank). After one minute of reaction time, reading was taken in (mg/L).

Heavy metal analysis⁴ :

The following metals were analysed using double beam Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer Perkin-Elmer USA

make model no. 372. The absorbance for cadmium was measured at 229 nm, chromium was measured at 358 nm, copper measured at 325 nm, manganese at 279.5 nm, iron at 348.3 nm, lead at 283.3 nm, zinc at 328 nm wavelength.

Results and discussion

Air environment :

The criteria taken into account in the design of ambient air quality monitoring network were the priority area for air monitoring were identified by running the screening air quality models like PTMAX (Point Maximum), PTPLU (Point Plume) and PTDIS (Point Distance), PAL (Point Area and Line)³ and using available meteorological data, topography/terrain of the study area, density of population within the region, residential and sensitive areas, magnitude of surrounding activities, wind direction and wind speed. To establish the existing baseline air quality status of the air basin, around Kadipani region, various Ambient Air Quality Monitoring (AAQM) stations were selected in different directions of proposed project site as per guidelines of network sitting criteria. Based on the nature of mining activities and various other activities within the study area, the conventional air pollutant Suspended Particulate Matter was identified as significant pollutants for ambient air quality monitoring.

During the summer season, the 95th percentile value of 24 hourly concentration of SPM was found to be in the range of 98.2 to 169.6 µg/m³. The maximum observed SPM concentration of 172.0 µg/m³ was found at Raisingpura. It is attributed to vehicular movement on road. The minimum observed SPM of 70 µg/m³ was found at Mongra. The SPM concentration observed Ambadungar mine site was in the range of 77 to 122 µg/m³ which is well within the stipulated regulatory limits. The different percentiles along with minimum and maximum SPM concentrations observed in the study area are given in Table 1.

Water environment :

Ground water quality :

Eleven ground water samples were collected from different villages surrounding the project site and analysis was carried out. The results obtained for ground water quality for physical and inorganic parameters², heavy metals at different identified locations are given in

Table 1. Observed values of ambient SPM concentration (Summer season)

Sl. no.	Sampling stations	Min. obs.	24 hourly average, Unit : $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$			Max. obs.
			Percentile			
			25	50	95	
1.	Proposed mine site (core zone)	77.0	93.0	105.0	120.8	122.0
2.	Padar	80.0	90.1	115.9	128.5	132.0
3.	Mongra	70.0	74.8	82.9	98.26	100.0
4.	Kadipani village	93.0	100.0	109.2	126.7	128.0
5.	Fluorspar beneficiation plant	125.0	133.6	146.5	165.4	168.0
6.	Kakanpur	117.0	131.2	152.1	165.2	167.0
7.	Raisingpura	107.0	121.1	142.4	169.6	172.0
8.	Umti	92.0	99.3	114.1	133.9	136.2

Table 2.1. Ground water – physical parameters (Summer season)

Sl. no.	Location	pH	Turbidity (NTU)	Conductivity (mS/cm)	T.D.S.	S.S.	T.S.
					(mg/L)		
1.	Mongra	7.4	1.04	1.09	465	18	483
2.	Bunjar	8.4	3.09	1.25	490	28	518
3.	Raisingpura	8.7	1.00	1.19	486	24	510
4.	Umti	8.6	1.94	0.74	362	52	414
5.	Bakhatgarh	8.2	0.76	0.62	300	16	316
6.	Wazirpur	8.4	1.00	0.57	279	36	315
7.	Kawant	7.7	1.45	0.90	439	36	475
8.	Rajawant	8.0	1.25	1.24	485	16	501
9.	Padwani	8.2	1.67	0.72	353	24	377
10.	Kadipani village	8.4	1.69	0.61	298	24	322
11.	Ambadungar mine site (core zone)	7.2	2.45	0.82	402	48	450

Table 2.2. Ground water – inorganic parameters (Summer season)

Sl. no.	Location	Alkalinity as CaCO_3	Hardness as CaCO_3			SO_4^{2-}	Cl^-	NO_3^-	F^-
			T	Ca	Mg				
			1.	Mongra	484				
2.	Bunjar	266	221	166	55	66	215	0.8	1.6
3.	Raisingpura	218	101	92	9	80	200	1.6	1.8
4.	Umti	190	28	18	10	80	78	0.6	1.0
5.	Bakhatgarh	285	120	74	46	16	73	0.4	0.7
6.	Wazirpur	209	74	64	10	28	59	0.9	1.0
7.	Kawant	266	258	184	74	30	78	0.3	0.8
8.	Rajawant	399	221	110	111	115	122	0.3	1.2
9.	Padwani	314	230	156	74	10	29	1.4	1.7
10.	Kadipani village	288	92	46	46	23	54	1.2	1.3
11.	Ambadungar mine site	152	337	258	79	18	34	1.6	1.9

Note : All values expressed in mg/L.

Tables 2.1, 2.2 and 2.3 respectively. Analytical results indicate variation² of pH in the range of 7.2 to 8.7. The conductivity values were in the range of 0.57 mS/cm to 1.25 mS/cm. The turbidity values were found in the range of 0.76 NTU to 3.09 NTU. Total dissolved solids observed were in the range of 279 mg/L to 490 mg/L and suspended solids varied from 16 mg/L to 52 mg/L.

The sulphate and chloride values³ were found to be between of 10 mg/L to 115 mg/L and 29 mg/L to 215 mg/L respectively. The concentration of nitrate and fluoride shows variation in the range of 0.3 mg/L to 1.6 mg/L and 0.7 mg/L to 1.9 mg/L respectively. Total hardness has been found in the range of 28 mg/L to 451 mg/L

slightly higher value of total hardness is observed in Mongra and Ambadungar mine site. The heavy metals are found in considerably low concentrations. Chromium and cadmium were present in non-detectable range in all the ground water samples. Results of heavy metal analysis are given in Table 2.3.

Surface water quality :

Four surface water samples were collected and analysed. The results obtained for physico-chemical parameters viz. physical, inorganic, organic and nutrient parameter, for heavy metals are given in Tables 2.4, 2.5, 2.6 and 2.7 respectively.

Table 2.3. Ground water – heavy metals (Summer season)

Sl. no.	Location	Fe	Cu	Mn	Pb	Zn	Cr	Cd
1.	Mongra	0.15	0.10	0.18	0.01	0.21	ND	ND
2.	Bunjar	0.83	0.27	0.19	ND	0.10	ND	ND
3.	Raisingpura	0.14	0.18	0.07	0.01	0.18	0.01	ND
4.	Umti	0.96	0.16	0.18	ND	0.08	ND	ND
5.	Bakhatgarh	0.16	0.10	0.09	ND	0.01	ND	ND
6.	Wazirpur	0.11	0.11	0.12	ND	0.06	0.01	ND
7.	Kawant	0.13	0.17	0.16	0.03	0.10	0.01	ND
8.	Rajawant	0.14	0.16	0.07	ND	0.11	0.01	ND
9.	Padwani	0.17	0.10	0.11	ND	0.05	ND	ND
10.	Kadipani village	0.22	0.08	0.22	0.02	0.02	ND	ND
11.	Ambadungar mine site	0.11	0.36	0.08	0.01	0.04	ND	ND

Note : All values expressed in mg/L.

Table 2.4. Surface water – physical parameters (Summer season)

Sl. no.	Location	pH	Turbidity (NTU)	Conductivity (mS/cm)	T.D.S.	S.S.	T.S.
					(mg/L)		
1.	Mathwad nallah	8.2	1.26	0.43	207	36	243
2.	Narmada river	8.1	2.23	0.27	130	52	182
3.	Inlet-water treatment plant	8.3	1.76	0.55	265	32	297
4.	Treated water to mine site	7.6	1.35	0.46	223	24	247

Table 2.5. Surface water – inorganic parameters (Summer season)

Sl. no.	Location	Alkalinity as CaCO ₃	Hardness as CaCO ₃			SO ₄ ²⁻	Cl ⁻	NO ₃ ⁻	F ⁻
			T	Ca	Mg				
			1.	Mathwad nallah	399				
2.	Narmada river	180	122	74	48	7	15	0.02	1.1
3.	Inlet-water treatment plant	133	193	101	92	26	24	0.02	1.2
4.	Treated water to mine site	142	184	101	83	13	15	0.01	0.57

Note : All values are expressed in mg/L.

Table 2.6. Surface water – organic and nutrient parameter (Summer season)

Sl. no.	Location	DO	COD	PO ₄ ³⁻
1.	Mathwad nallah	6.5	18	0.73
2.	Narmada river	7.4	16	0.52
3.	Inlet-water treatment plant	7.8	12	1.25
4.	Treated water to mine site	8.1	10	0.65

Note : All values are expressed in mg/L.

treated water to Ambadunger mine site. Total hardness was found to be reduced from 193 mg/L to 184 mg/L. The concentration of chloride was reduced from 24 mg/L to 15 mg/L, sulphate was reduced from 26 mg/L to 13 mg/L and fluoride was reduced from 1.2 mg/L to 0.57 mg/L in treated water to Ambadunger mine site in comparison to inlet to water treatment plant. The alkalinity⁵ has been found to be 399 and 180 mg/L in sample of surface water collected from Mathwad nallah and Narmada

Table 2.7. Surface water – heavy metals (Summer season)

Sl. no.	Location	Fe	Cu	Mn	Pb	Zn	Cr	Cd
1.	Mathwad nallah	0.15	0.11	0.19	0.01	0.08	0.01	ND
2.	Narmada river	0.22	0.11	0.16	ND	0.03	ND	ND
3.	Inlet-water treatment plant	0.26	0.10	0.14	ND	0.01	ND	ND
4.	Treated water to mine site	0.09	0.11	0.12	0.01	0.03	ND	ND

Note : All values are expressed in mg/L.

The pH of the inlet to water treatment plant and treated water to mine site has been found to be 8.3 and 7.6. Turbidity has been found reduced from 1.76 NTU to 1.35 NTU in treated water to mine site. Conductivity has been reduced from 0.55 mS/cm to 0.46 mS/cm, total dissolved solids have been reduced from 265 mg/L to 223 mg/L and suspended solids have been reduced from 32 mg/L to 24 mg/L in treated water mine site in comparison to inlet to water treatment plant.

The pH of surface water sample of Mathwad nallah and Narmada river was found to be 8.2 and 8.1. Turbidity and conductivity⁴ were found to be 1.26 NTU and 2.23 NTU and 0.43 mS/cm and 0.27 mS/cm respectively in these samples. Total dissolved solids have been found to be 207 mg/L and 130 mg/L and suspended solids were 36 mg/L and 52 mg/L.

The alkalinity has been found to be 133 mg/L and 142 mg/L in the samples of inlet to water treatment plant and

river. Total hardness, sulphate and chloride were found to be 156 mg/L and 122 mg/L, 13 mg/L and 7 mg/L and 34 mg/L and 15 mg/L respectively. The concentration of fluoride is 1.1 mg/L in both the samples.

From these results it can be concluded that the quality of air, water and soil samples is well within limits prescribed by the statutory authorities.

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